

Visibility and invisibility of women contribution to environment

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Abstract

Recent study about women and science is a good source of material for addressing the under representation of women in science. This article is the result of an interdisciplinary fusion of science and women's studies in environment. Discipline demographics reveal that women are presented to textbooks less often expected and that explicit discussion of the social and cultural context is enriched with material about women's contributions, students' awareness of women scientists improves. Such knowledge of women can play a critical role in proactively challenging students' perceptions of ecology.

Keywords: Visibility; Invisibility; Women contribution; Environment

1. Introduction

Visibility of gender in biology shows the phenotype characters which differs the male and female separate. These are called sexes, denotes the men and women. But the concept of gender is different in other subjects. The gender perspective looks at the impact of gender on people's opportunities, social roles and interactions. Gender is an integral competent of every aspect of the economic, social, daily and private lives of individuals and societies and of the different roles ascribed by society to men and women.

Sex refers to the permanent and immutable biological characteristics common to individuals in all societies and cultures. Gender differences are social constructs, inculcated on the basis of a specific society's particular perceptions of the physical differences and the assumed tastes, tendencies and capabilities of men and women.

Gender relations are accordingly defined as the specific mechanisms whereby different cultures determine the functions and responsibilities of each sex. They also determine access to material resources, such as land, credit and training and more other resources.

2. Discussion

The impact of environmental degradation is gender differentiated in terms of workloads and the quality of life; women are the first to be affected by the depletion of natural resources. In developing countries, women are responsible for the daily management and use of natural resources, as well as providing for the family by raising food crops, gathering forest products and fetching wood and water. Widespread and growing deforestation and the drying up of water sources force women to range even further afield, spending more time and energy in producing and finding essential commodities and making it even harder for them to engage in more productive, more lucrative activities.

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Environmental degradation caused by poorly managed and utilized waste products and pollutants can have a disproportionate impact on women, who seem to be more susceptible to the toxic effects of certain chemicals. The health risk is even higher among the lower income strata of the population, who tend to live near industrial urban areas, are prayed from the air. Global warming, the shrinking ozone layer and reduced biodiversity are some of the better-known effects of environmental degradation.

Environmental degradation is most keenly felt by the most vulnerable members of the community and those who rely heavily on nature's bounty. For this region, gender disparities in natural resource management and participation in policy making must be clearly understood.

Women's relationship to the environment revolves around their central concern with household food security. Environmental degradation has a direct impact on women's workloads and get restricted access to inputs, resources, capital and employment often force women to over exploit the natural resources base. Despite this, rural women are both the best equipped and the worst equipped to manage the environment, the best because they have the necessary expertise and the worst because they lack the power to intervene. The expertise in the conservation and preservation of wild plants and animals that women have developed over time must be explored and these skills must be taken into account in policy formulation.

3. Conclusion

Women contribution towards environment is visible as well as invisible. Environmental degradation effects on the women's directly or indirectly as well as for environmental degradation some women factors are also affective. These factors may be unemployment or underemployment and unequal pay and work opportunities for women. Exclusion from or restricted participation in decision-making processes aimed at enhancing natural resource management unfavorable or discriminatory legislation etc.

The plan should be formulated to solve this problem, improve living standards, eradicate poverty among rural women and secure sustainable development.

Promoting policies, programmes and projects that improve rural women's access to and control over productive resources, inputs and services. Undertake research and action programmes to identify the legislative and policy changes needed to achieve gender equity in all sectors. Providing guidance and technical assistance to countries that are reorienting their agricultural policies, and reducing institutional barriers to women's access to land, capital, credit, extension, research, training, markets and producers' organizations.

Fostering awareness of the need to promote the participation and leadership of women in local, regional and national decision-making bodies;

Promoting the establishment of data exchange networks and ensuring that rural women's interests are represented in international and national policy-making. Supporting research, consultation and communication to ensure that women are considered as agents of change and not the passive beneficiaries of plans, projects and programmes.

Improved the production and dissemination of gender-responsive statistics so as to recognize and enhance the unpaid work of rural women, gain a better understand of the situation of rural men and women, and supply appropriate data for policy-making, planning and project formulation; supporting initiatives to address policies and practices that reinforce rural women's employment in food production, agriculture, forestry and fisheries; facilitating the utilization of productive and domestic labour-saving technologies. Enhancing rural women's income generating opportunities and access to agricultural education and more lucrative.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Akwa L, et al. Analysis of Fuel Wood Utilization Among Rural Women in Akwanga Area of Nasarawa State. Nigeria. The Abuja Journal of Geography and Development. 2008; 1(2).
- [2] Agrawal A. Women in Rural Society. Vohra Pub. & Distributors, Allahabad. 1998.
- [3] Agrawal B. Neither Sustenance Nor Sustainability-Agricultural Strategies Ecological Degradation and Indian Women in Poverty. In Bina Agrawal (Edi.); Structures of Patriarchy. Kali for Women, New Delhi. 1998.
- [4] Agrawal B. Gender and Forest Conservation-Impact of Women's Participation in Community Forest Governance. Ecological Economies, in Press. 2009.
- [5] Ali SM. Legal Aspects of Environmental Pollutions and It's Management, CBS Publishers, Delhi. 1999; 175.
- [6] Maye. Women: The Resource Managers. UNEP. 1994; 6(4): 23-24.
- [7] Mishra A. Chipko Movement: Uttrakhand Women's Bid to Save Forest Wealth. People's Action. New Delhi. 1978.
- [8] MKishra VS. Environmental Education and Awareness: The Indian Environment Perspective. Scavenger. 1993; 24(1): 9.
- [9] Mariama A, Henshall J. Gender and the Environment: Women's Time Use as a Measure of Environment Change. Global Environmental Change. 1995; 5: 337.
- [10] Nightingale A. The Nature of Gender Work, Gender and Environment Environment and Planning D: Society and Space. 2006; 24(2): 165-185.
- [11] Pryde. Environmental Chemistry: An Introduction. Cummings Publishing Company Inc. Philippines Press. 1994.
- [12] Women Success in Environmental Management. UNEP. Our Planet. 1992; 4(1): 16.
- [13] Tolb M. UNEP Changes for Past Two Decades and the Prospectus for the Future. UNEP. Our Planet. 1992; 4(6) 8-11.
- [14] Wenz Peter S. Environmental Ethics Today. New York: Oxford University Press. 2001.
- [15] WHO. Health Aspects Related to Indoor Air Quality, World Health Organization, Copehnhagen. 1979; 6.
- [16] Yamey. Gavin. The Bittersweet Sounds of the Modern Food Chain. Plos Biology. February 2006; 4(2): 165-166.